

**Peer Reviewed*

A Conceptual Framework for Exploring the Interconnections Between Housing and Health for Sustainable Development in South Africa. *Prisca Simbanegavi¹, Koech Cheruiyot¹, John Karuitha¹, Ezekiel Lengaram¹, Yewande Adewunmi¹.*

¹School of Construction Economics & Management, Faculty of Engineering & the Built Environment, New John Moffat Building, East Campus, 1 Jan Smuts Avenue, Braamfontein, Johannesburg (Prisca.Simbanegavi@wits.ac.za)

Abstract

Housing conditions are a critical social determinant of health, particularly in low and middle-income contexts such as South Africa, where historical inequalities and rapid urbanization contribute to persistent disparities. This study addresses the problem that, despite evidence linking housing to health outcomes, there is limited integrated conceptualization of how physical, socio-economic, environmental, and policy factors interact to shape health inequities in low-income urban settlements. The study aims to develop a conceptual framework that explains the interconnections between housing quality, affordability, stability, and safety, and their influence on physical and mental health outcomes. A desk-based rapid literature review was conducted using SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases, focusing on global frameworks from the WHO and UN-Habitat, African-specific scholarship, and empirical studies on housing and health. The resulting framework integrates physical, environmental, socio-economic, and policy dimensions, highlighting how structural deficiencies such as overcrowding, poor ventilation, inadequate sanitation, and insecure tenure do amplify vulnerability to communicable and non-communicable diseases. The findings provide a holistic lens for interdisciplinary research, guide empirical analysis, and inform policy integration between the housing and health sectors. Overall, the study demonstrates that improving housing systems is pivotal for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 6, and 11.

Keywords: Housing conditions; Health outcomes; Low-income settlements; Conceptual framework; South Africa; Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Introduction

The legacy of apartheid in South Africa continues to shape housing conditions and access to essential services. During the apartheid era, legislation such as the Group Areas Act systematically denied Black South Africans access to adequate housing, relegating them to overcrowded and under-resourced townships (Marais, 2013). The apartheid era policies of forced removals and spatial segregation gave rise to informal settlements and low-income townships that continue to suffer from insufficient infrastructure and public services (Seekings, 2011). This spatial segregation reinforced socio-economic disparities, resulting in generations of Black South Africans enduring inadequate living conditions with limited access to health-supporting infrastructure (Gbadegesin, 2020; Moyo et al., 2021; Marais et al., 2018; Stull, Bell and Ncwadi, 2016). These environments foster persistent poverty, unemployment, and poor health outcomes (Kahn et al., 2017). According to Kararachi (2024), the spatial outcomes of apartheid have produced a dual economy, wherein developed, affluent urban centers coexist with underdeveloped townships, informal settlements, and impoverished rural areas. This strong duality contributes to South Africa's status as one of the most unequal societies globally, with persistent disparities based on space, race, and gender demonstrating how inadequate housing engenders a vicious cycle of physical, mental, and social deprivation, particularly for already marginalized populations (Smith, 2023). Urbanization on the other hand, compounds these pressures, with 69% of the population now residing in rapidly expanding urban areas (Turok, Todes and Smit, 2022). Thus, the consequences of spatial inequality extend into health, with socio-economic status and living conditions serving as major determinants of health

outcomes that impact on the United Nations Sustainable Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11.

Data from the Centre for Affordable Housing Finance in Africa (CAHF, 2024) highlights that, as of the 2022 Census, South Africa's population of 62 million people live in 17.8 million households, with an average household size of 3.5 people. While the proportion of formal dwellings has increased from 65.1% in 1996 to 88.5% in 2022, nearly one-third of households still rely on government-subsidized housing, underscoring persistent housing shortages and quality challenges. Despite considerable improvements in service provision, such as piped water access increasing to 82.4%, flush toilets to 70.8%, and electricity access nearing 95% of households, many communities still face inadequate living conditions (CAHF, 2024). Historical legacies and structural inequality continue to produce uneven housing outcomes, with systemic issues such as unaffordability, poor quality, limited access to services, energy poverty and weak policy implementation further constraining the wellbeing of people (Smith, 2023; Stull, Bell and Newadi, 2016).

Housing quality is a critical determinant of public health, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where poor housing exacerbates health inequalities and reinforces socio-economic exclusion (Masuku, 2024). The South African case strongly illustrates how historical injustices, and current inequalities intersect to produce profound disparities in housing and health exacerbating widespread housing inadequacy marked by overcrowding, substandard sanitation, and heightened exposure to environmental hazards (Katukiza et al., 2012). Extensive research confirms that housing conditions are a major determinant of health (Kawachi and Berkman, 2001). Substandard housing, characterized by overcrowding, dampness, and lack of ventilation, has been linked to respiratory illnesses, mental health issues, and increased risk of infectious diseases (Sharif et al., 2024; Evans et al., 2003). Conversely, well-designed and adequately serviced housing contributes positively to physical and mental health and overall well-being (Whitehead et al., 2019).

The relationship between housing and health is multifaceted. In South Africa, addressing housing inequality is vital to promoting health equity. Barriers to adequate housing remain significant for marginalized populations, who often dedicate a disproportionate share of their income to housing costs, at the expense of other essentials such as food and healthcare (Habib et al., 2025). These financial burdens are intensified by energy poverty, which forces households to use harmful energy sources, with further health implications (Culwick & Khanyile, 2023; Guerra, and Eboime, 2021; Musango, 2014). Housing inadequacy, especially in urban contexts, is a major driver of health disparities. Overcrowded, poorly ventilated, and structurally unsound housing can lead to a range of adverse health outcomes, including respiratory infections, communicable diseases, and mental health challenges (Connolly et al., 2004; World Health Organization, 2018). Housing conditions are a critical social determinant of health, particularly in low and middle-income contexts such as South Africa, where historical inequalities and rapid urbanization contribute to persistent disparities. This study addresses the problem that, despite evidence linking housing to health outcomes, there is limited integrated conceptualization of how physical, socio-economic, environmental, and policy factors interact to shape health inequities in low-income urban settlements. The study aims to develop a conceptual framework that explains the interconnections between housing quality, affordability, stability, and safety, and their influence on physical and mental health outcomes. The interconnections between housing and health in South Africa are complex and

multifaceted, involving various SDGs, particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11. The question that begs is how this complexity can be conceptualized with the aim of harmonizing the approaches that are crucial for sustainable development through a conceptual framework.

Theoretical review of literature

This section covers theoretical perspectives on housing inadequacy and health. This section concludes with a conceptual framework to explore the interconnections between housing and health for sustainable development, particularly the United Nations Sustainable Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3, SDG 6, and SDG 11 in the context of South Africa. This study draws upon four main perspectives that include the Social Determinants of Health (SDH), the Environmental Health Model, Vulnerability Theory, and the Ecological Model.

Social Determinants of Health (SDH)

The Social Determinants of Health (SDH) framework posits that socio-economic conditions, including housing quality, are fundamental drivers of health outcomes (Kawachi & Berkman, 2001). Housing inadequacy is considered a proxy for broader social disadvantage, influencing physical and mental health through environmental exposures and psychosocial stressors (Swope, & Hernández, 2019; Marmot et al., 2010). Low-income households often reside in informal settlements where access to clean water, sanitation, and healthcare is limited, compounding their health vulnerabilities (Kann et al., 2024; Culwick & Khanyile, 2023). Empirical studies reinforce the SDH framework by linking substandard housing to high incidences of infectious diseases, such as cholera and tuberculosis, and respiratory illnesses such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Holden et al., 2023).

Mental health issues, including stress, anxiety, and depression, are also prevalent among individuals living in unstable or overcrowded housing conditions (Sharif & Dey, 2024). These health disparities are intensified by economic hardship, which not only affects housing conditions but also limits access to necessary healthcare services (Culwick & Khanyile, 2023). SDG 3 emphasises good health and well-being indicating that health outcomes emanate from housing conditions. Poor housing is linked to adverse health effects, including mental health issues and general well-being (Shortt and Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022; Ntema et al., 2021).

Environmental Health Model

The environmental health model emphasizes the direct physiological impacts of substandard housing conditions, such as inadequate ventilation, use of hazardous materials such as asbestos, dampness, and overcrowding (Kua & Lee, 2021). These structural deficiencies are closely associated with increased rates of respiratory infections, especially among children who are more susceptible to indoor pollutants. In the South African context, the use of solid fuels for cooking and heating in inadequately ventilated homes exacerbates indoor air pollution, contributing to chronic respiratory illnesses, affecting respiration in children (Liu et al., 2024). Poor sanitation and insufficient solid waste management further facilitate the spread of communicable diseases, such as cholera and diarrhoea infections (Narayan et al., 2021). Overcrowding and poor insulation in informal settlements lead to cold, damp environments where mould thrives, conditions strongly linked to asthma and other respiratory issues (Wimalasena et al., 2021). The environmental health burdens of inadequate housing are

compounded by noise pollution and neighbourhood disorder, which further aggravate mental health conditions (Masuku & Nzewi, 2021; Haselbach et al., 2009).

Vulnerability Theory

Vulnerability theory underscores how socio-politically marginalised populations are disproportionately exposed to housing inadequacy and its associated health risks (Masuku, 2024). In the South African post-apartheid context, historical patterns of segregation and economic exclusion have rendered informal settlement dwellers especially vulnerable. This framework highlights systemic inequities in access to adequate housing, clean energy, and essential services. This is because adequate housing must include access to clean water and sanitation (SDG 6). The lack of these services in informal settlements exacerbates health vulnerability (Ntema et al., 2021; Buthelezi et al., 2024; Tusting, et al., 2019). Improved housing with better sanitation facilities can significantly enhance health and well-being (Ntema et al., 2021).

Despite policy interventions such as the Integrated National Electrification Programme (INEP), energy poverty persists, reducing the ability of households to access clean energy for cooking and heating, thereby worsening health outcomes (Samarakoon, 2019; Broto, 2028; Ismail & Khembo, 2015). Globally, similar patterns are evident. For instance, in Canada, First Nations communities experiencing damp, mould-infested housing report higher respiratory illness prevalence than the general population (Waddell et al., 2024). These disparities reaffirm the core tenet of vulnerability theory, that housing inadequacy both reflects and reinforces broader social inequities.

Ecological Model

The ecological model adds a layered understanding by emphasizing how health is influenced by the interaction of individual, community, and environmental factors (Balashova et al., 2025; Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Inadequate housing impacts not only physical health through exposure to environmental hazards but also mental and social wellbeing by introducing stress, instability, and reduced social cohesion. This model is particularly valuable in highlighting the cumulative and interactive nature of housing-related health risks. For example, the stress of living in unstable housing situations can exacerbate anxiety and depression (Sharif & Dey, 2024), while also weakening immune responses, making individuals more susceptible to infections. In the South African context, these frameworks converge to portray a grim reality where structural deficits, poverty, and systemic inequities band together to exacerbate public health problems and violating SDG 11. Poorly located housing developments can limit economic opportunities and perpetuate inequality (Culwick & Patel, 2020). Studies show that overcrowding and unsanitary living conditions in informal settlements contribute to the transmission of communicable diseases such as tuberculosis and diarrhoea (Penrose et al., 2010; Moffa et al., 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic further exposed how housing inadequacy, particularly overcrowding and lack of isolation spaces do facilitate disease transmission, especially in high-density urban areas (Corburn et al., 2020; Nyashanu et al., 2020). The compounded effects of energy poverty, environmental exposures, and socio-economic stressors remain underexplored, suggesting a crucial area for future research to aid policy intervention.

Empirical literature review

Inadequate housing conditions have consistently been linked to a broad spectrum of diseases and health complications. This arises from multiple dimensions of housing inadequacy, that include overcrowding, poor sanitation, environmental hazards, structural instability, and insufficient access to clean water and safe materials. The World Health Organization (2018) emphasizes that in low and middle-income countries, where substandard housing is prevalent, the resultant health risks are particularly severe. Poor housing not only compromises physical health but also negatively affects mental and social well-being, underscoring its role as a critical determinant of public health outcomes (Usha & Nithiya, 2024). Access to health services is crucial. Improved integration of health services (SDG 3, 6 and 11) in housing policies can lead to better health outcomes (Ntema et al., 2021).

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 3, 6 & 9), housing & health

Good health and well-being (SDG 3) focusses on health outcomes indicating housing conditions significantly impact health outcomes. Poor housing, especially in informal settlements, is linked to adverse health effects, including mental health issues and general well-being (Shortt and Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022; Ntema et al., 2021). Upgrading housing can improve mental health and community satisfaction (Shortt & Hammett, 2013). Access to health services is crucial. Improved integration of health services in housing policies can lead to better health outcomes (Ntema et al., 2021).

Clean water and sanitation (SDG 6) focusses on sanitation and water access, indicating that adequate housing must include access to clean water and sanitation. The lack of these services in informal settlements exacerbates health issues (Buthelezi et al., 2024; Tusting, et al., 2019). Improved housing with better sanitation facilities can significantly enhance health and well-being (Tusting et al., 2019).

Sustainable cities and communities (SDG 11) focus on inclusive and safe housing indicating that creating inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable human settlements is a core objective of this goal. This includes providing adequate housing and basic services (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). The transformation of housing in urban and rural areas has shown improvements, but many still live in inadequate conditions in South Africa (Tusting et al., 2019). Thus, sustainable urban development involves addressing housing quality, access to services, and environmental sustainability (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). Poorly located housing developments can limit economic opportunities and perpetuate inequality (Culwick & Patel, 2020). This paper identifies eight categories of diseases linked to housing conditions covered below.

(i) Respiratory Diseases

A significant body of evidence links poor housing conditions with the onset and exacerbation of respiratory diseases, that include asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and acute respiratory infections (ARIs) (Azanaw et al., 2024). Poor indoor air quality, driven by dampness, mould, tobacco smoke, and inadequate ventilation has been widely recognized as a major risk factor (Aftab et al., 2022). Mold and dust mites, common in poorly ventilated and damp environments, trigger allergic responses and are linked to asthma development. Children are particularly vulnerable, with studies showing increased ARI symptoms among those living in homes with natural material floors or exposed to wood and coal heating, especially in countries like Pakistan and Ethiopia (Andualem et al., 2020).

Overcrowding exacerbates these risks by promoting the spread of airborne pathogens (Rennie and Lawson 2011). In settings such as disaster shelters and military barracks, insufficient ventilation and unhygienic living conditions have been directly associated with respiratory infections like tuberculosis (Shahzad, 2025; Adam et al., 2010). After the Türkiye and Syria earthquake, temporary shelters lacking clean water and sanitation facilities saw spikes in respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, underscoring how emergency housing conditions can intensify disease transmission (Smith, 2023; Yasui & Numada, 2021). Poor environmental health conditions in shelters include unhygienic bedding and lack of infrastructure also facilitate the spread of respiratory illnesses (Kishore et al., 2023). Such exposures are not only physical health risks but also have implications for mental health, as environmental stressors like pollution have been associated with elevated rates of depression (Parikh et al., 2022). Children living in inadequate housing often face dual risks of respiratory illness and psychological distress. Indoor exposures to tobacco smoke, mould, and other pollutants are especially harmful for children, who may develop chronic respiratory conditions and psychological distress because of prolonged exposure (Wu et al., 2024).

(ii) Infectious Diseases

Infectious diseases thrive in overcrowded and unsanitary living environments. Overcrowding increases interpersonal contact, which accelerates the spread of diseases such as tuberculosis, cholera, and gastroenteritis (Herath et al., 2024; Sharif, and Kanti, 2024). Poor sanitation and contaminated water sources further compound these risks, particularly in informal settlements and shelters that lack proper sewage systems (Echazú et al., 2015). The COVID-19 pandemic sharply revealed how overcrowded housing facilitates disease transmission. In urban settings like southwestern Sydney, households experiencing high levels of overcrowding exhibited elevated COVID-19 infection rates (Herath et al., 2024; Nyashanu et al., 2020). Health inequities persist in impoverished communities where poor housing is often accompanied by limited access to water and healthcare. Abrams et al., (2021) and Sharma et al., (2013) assert that such inequities not only elevate infection risks but also intensify mental health issues. Beyond respiratory and gastrointestinal infections, inadequate housing has been linked to viral diseases such as lassa fever, which is transmitted by rodents in structurally unsound homes (Kelly et al., 2013). There are also COVID-19 and influenza outbreaks in overcrowded shelters (Gazin and Brouqui, 2004). Bacterial infections also flourish in substandard housing. Pathogens such as staphylococcus aureus spread rapidly due to poor hygiene and close contact among residents, especially in shelters lacking adequate sanitation infrastructure (Shukla et al., 2020). Tuberculosis transmission is heightened in densely populated and poorly ventilated shelters.

(iii) Vector-Borne Diseases

Housing conditions that lack adequate drainage, clean water access, and sealed construction invite vectors such as mosquitoes, significantly increasing the risk of diseases such as malaria and dengue fever (Narayan et al., 2021). These diseases are particularly severe in urban informal settlements, where standing water and open waste attract disease vectors. Vector-borne diseases such as bartonellosis, chagas disease, and leishmaniasis are closely tied to unsanitary and overcrowded housing environments. These diseases are especially prevalent among homeless and displaced populations, who are more frequently exposed to insects and rodents due to lack of protective barriers and proper housing structures (Ralli et al., 2021; Karb et al., 2020).

(iv) Mental Health Problems

The psychosocial stressors inherent in poor housing such as insecurity, overcrowding, and environmental degradation significantly contribute to mental health disorders including anxiety, depression, and stress-related illnesses (Leta, 2021). Exposure to mould, dampness, and pollutants does not only cause physical illness but also elevates psychological distress (Parikh et al., 2022). Children living in these environments are doubly affected, with increased susceptibility to mental health disorders due to the compounding stressors of illness and environment. Living in insecure or inadequate housing also disrupts family functioning, reduces educational performance among children, and increases exposure to violence, all of which contribute to poor mental health outcomes.

(v) Chronic Diseases

Liu et al., (2024) finds long-term exposure to environmental stressors such as mould, chemical pollutants, and poor air quality in inadequate housing environments can lead to chronic conditions that include cardiovascular diseases, hypertension, and metabolic disorders. These chronic illnesses are often compounded by limited access to healthcare and a lack of resources for disease management, especially in low-income populations. Furthermore, poor housing design that promotes sedentary lifestyles, such as lack of recreational spaces and safe walking paths also contributes to chronic health conditions. The cumulative stress from poor housing conditions serves as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease by disrupting sleep, increasing anxiety, and fostering unhealthy behaviors.

(vi) Injuries and Accidents

Substandard housing poses numerous physical safety hazards that increase the risk of injuries and accidents. These include structural instability, unsafe staircases, poorly installed electrical wiring, and lack of smoke detectors. Falls, burns, and electrocutions are more prevalent in inadequately maintained housing, especially informal settlements (Nuwagaba, 2018). Children and the elderly are especially at risk due to mobility limitations and lack of proper safety features in their homes. Poor lighting, uneven flooring, and obstructed pathways further contribute to home-related injuries. In regions prone to natural disasters, poorly constructed housing is also more susceptible to collapse, placing residents at higher risk of injury or death during earthquakes or floods (Ergönül et al., 2021).

(vii) Lead Poisoning and Waterborne Diseases

Inadequate housing often contains outdated infrastructure, including lead-based paint and plumbing, which can result in lead poisoning, particularly in children. Exposure to lead has been linked to cognitive impairment, developmental delays, and behavioral problems (Guerra, and Eboreime, 2021). Ortega, (2021) finds a decreased brain volume in adults with childhood lead exposure. Contaminated water systems, often found in informal settlements, are another critical risk factor, leading to waterborne diseases such as typhoid, cholera, and dysentery (Ali, Foster and Hall, 2018). These diseases flourish in environments, where housing lacks reliable water supply and sanitation.

(viii) Cancer and Skin Conditions

The use of hazardous building materials, especially asbestos, in roofing and insulation is strongly associated with various forms of cancer. Asbestos exposure can lead to asbestosis, a

chronic respiratory condition and is a major risk factor for lung cancer and mesothelioma, a rare cancer affecting the lungs and abdominal lining (Reid et al., 2021; Carbone et al., 2022). Additional cancers linked to asbestos exposure include cancers of the larynx and ovary (Hodgson, 2020; van Mark, 2007; Cohen et al., 2023). In response to these well-documented health risks, the World Health Organization (2022) supports bans or restrictions on the use of asbestos in construction. Skin conditions are another overlooked consequence of inadequate housing. Poor sanitation and water access contribute to dermatological issues such as scabies, fungal infections, and dermatitis, especially in crowded and humid living environments (Chastonay & Chastonay, 2022). These conditions often go untreated in underserved populations, exacerbating discomfort and facilitating secondary infections.

Methodology

A desk-based rapid literature review was conducted using SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases, focusing on global frameworks from the WHO and UN-Habitat, African-specific scholarship, and empirical studies on housing and health. A rapid literature survey was conducted via SCOPUS and EBSCO HOST databases. These two databases were chosen because they are the largest abstract and citation sources of peer-reviewed literature. Using the topic called “housing conditions and health outcomes” and five key words (housing and human rights, socio-economic factors and health, environment and health, the categories of housing associated with housing inadequacy) as string of words, the search yielded 250 sources consisting of journals, books, and conference proceedings that gave relevant information on the study. 97 sources were found to be relevant in conceptualizing housing conditions and health outcomes as an output of this study, specified in figure 1.

Theoretical underpinnings

Theoretical and empirical evidence converge to demonstrate that housing inadequacy is not merely a shelter issue, but a multidimensional determinant of health shown in figure 1. As emphasized by Marmot et al., (2010), research necessitates a cross-sectoral approach that embeds health considerations within housing policy, ensuring adequate infrastructure, sanitation, ventilation, and energy access to promote holistic well-being (Smith, 2023). As emphasized by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2018), inadequate housing is closely linked to a broad spectrum of health issues that include respiratory illnesses, mental health disorders, and infectious diseases.

Findings: The conceptual framework

The resulting framework integrates physical, environmental, socio-economic, and policy dimensions, highlighting how structural deficiencies such as overcrowding, poor ventilation, inadequate sanitation, and insecure tenure do amplify vulnerability to communicable and non-communicable diseases. At the core of the framework lies the interconnection between key housing dimensions, quality, affordability, stability, and safety and their cumulative impact on health. Housing quality refers to the structural integrity and functionality of a dwelling, including aspects such as ventilation, presence of mould or pests, heating, and sanitation. The physical structure of housing and the surrounding environment play a critical role in residents' health. Poor housing conditions can lead to both physical and mental health issues (Shortt & Hammett, 2013; Chatindiara et al., 2022). Deteriorating conditions in these domains are strongly associated with adverse physical health outcomes, particularly respiratory ailments such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Holden et al., 2023; Wu et al.,

2024). Affordability, defined as the cost of housing relative to household income, determines the extent to which households can allocate resources to other health, promoting essentials like nutrition, healthcare, and education. Excessive housing costs may force trade-offs that compromise overall well-being (Avčín et al., 2011). Jabali et al., 2025 found smaller households, with higher family incomes, and in private homes report better health.

Stability, another critical dimension, reflects the frequency and predictability of residential arrangements. Housing improvements can foster a sense of belonging and community cohesion, which are important for mental health and overall well-being (Shortt & Hammett, 2013). High levels of housing instability, including frequent relocations and homelessness, can disrupt daily routines and social networks, contributing to heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and depression (Sharif & Dey, 2024; Rogers et al., 2023; Kua & Lee, 2021; Ghinai et al., 2020). Furthermore, safety encompasses both the physical security of the built environment and the broader neighborhood context, including exposure to crime, environmental hazards, and accidents. Insecure and hazardous settings perpetuate chronic stress and increase vulnerability to both physical injuries and long-term psychological distress.

Socioeconomic status (SES) intersects with housing conditions, serving as a crucial social determinant of health. Lower SES, marked by constrained income, limited education, and unstable employment, often correlates with substandard housing and increased health risks (Anwar et al., 2021). Residents of informal settlements and overcrowded dwellings face a heightened likelihood of exposure to environmental health threats, including infectious disease transmission and insufficient access to healthcare services (Masuku, 2024). In this context, economic stressors such as unemployment and financial crises have been shown to exacerbate psychiatric morbidity (Nvo-Fernandez et al., 2025). For instance, the Greek financial crisis led to a noticeable rise in major depression rates, underscoring the influence of broader economic dynamics on mental health (Economou et al., 2018).

Environmental factors further compound the effects of housing inadequacy. These include neighborhood characteristics such as pollution levels, access to green spaces, and proximity to community resources (Kyne, 2023). Environmental degradation and poor air quality are particularly detrimental, serving as catalysts for respiratory illnesses and mental health conditions (Haselbach et al., 2009). Informal settlements, where poverty and overcrowding prevail, face unique challenges in implementing disease prevention and control measures, leading to elevated rates of infectious disease and compounding physical and mental health challenges. Sustainable housing must consider environmental impacts, such as resource consumption and carbon emissions. Adaptive reuse of buildings is one strategy to mitigate these impacts while addressing housing needs (Owojori et al., 2024). The cyclical and bidirectional nature of the relationship between housing and health is also evident. Poor health can undermine a household's ability to secure and maintain adequate housing, while housing inadequacy exacerbates health vulnerabilities (Marmot et al., 2010). This interdependence illustrates the self-reinforcing cycle of housing-related health inequities. Mental health, while traditionally overlooked in housing literature, warrants particular attention in marginalized populations. The mental health consequences of unstable, unsafe, and inadequate housing include heightened stress, depression, anxiety, and a diminished sense of agency or belonging (Sharif & Dey, 2024; Masuku & Nzewi, 2021). Environmental stressors such as noise, overcrowding, and social isolation contribute further to psychological strain, particularly in dense urban environments and informal settlements.

Figure 1: The interconnection between housing conditions, health outcomes & SDG 3, 6 & 9 conceptual framework

Source: authors

Discussion

There is a need for better integration of health considerations into housing policies. Current policies often overlook the health outcomes of housing interventions required to improve people’s wellbeing (Ntema et al., 2021). Efforts must be directed towards marginalized communities to ensure they benefit from sustainable development initiatives. This includes improving access to health services, sanitation, and adequate housing (Ntema et al., 2021; Buthelezi et al., 2024). By and large, achieving sustainable development goals requires collaboration between the state, community, private sector, and other stakeholders (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024). The framework shows that multicomponent and cross-sectoral interventions are essential to effectively address the complex interplay of housing and health in ways that fulfil SDGs 3, 6 and 11 (Leboto-Khetsi et al., 2024; Narayan et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The findings provide a holistic lens for interdisciplinary research, guide empirical analysis, and inform policy integration between the housing and health sectors. This conceptual framework underscores that housing is not merely a place of shelter but a critical site of health production if built with health outcomes in mind (Turley et al., 2013). It emphasizes that physical and mental health outcomes are not only determined by the built environment but are deeply embedded in social and environmental contexts shaped by economic hardship, policy choices, and historical inequities. Comprehensive strategies that integrate housing improvements with social support systems and equitable policy reforms are vital for promoting health equity and breaking the vicious cycle of poor housing and ill health. Overall, the study recommends

improving housing systems as it is pivotal for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 6, and 11, and for promoting equitable health outcomes in South Africa and the Global South.

Disclosure Statement: No potential conflict of interest.

ORCID

Prisca Simbanegavi1 [0000-0001-7238-3731](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7238-3731)

Koech Cheruiyot2 [0000-0003-2247-2802](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2247-2802)

John Karuitha3 [0000-0002-8204-7034](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8204-7034)

Ezekiel Lengaram4 [0000-0001-5643-9221](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5643-9221)

Yewande Adewunmi5 [0000-0002-0318-3370](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0318-3370)

References

Abrams, A.L., Carden, K., Teta, C. and Wågsæther, K. 2021. Water, sanitation, and hygiene vulnerability among rural areas and small towns in South Africa: Exploring the role of climate change, marginalization, and inequality. *Water (Switzerland)*, 13 (20). doi:10.3390/w13202810.

Acosta-España, J.D., Romero-Alvarez, D., Luna, C. and Rodriguez-Morales, A.J. 2024. Infectious disease outbreaks in the wake of natural flood disasters: global patterns and local implications. *Infezioni in Medicina*, 32(4), pp.451–462.

Adam, H.J., Guthrie, J.L., Bolotin, S., Alexander, D.C., Stuart, R., Pyskir, D., Brown, E.M., Rea, E., Chedore, P. and Jamieson, F.B. 2010. Genotypic characterization of tuberculosis transmission within Toronto's under-housed population, 1997–2008. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, 14(10), pp.1350–1353.

Aftab, A., Noor, A. and Aslam, M. 2022. Housing quality and its impact on Acute Respiratory Infection (ARI) symptoms among children in Punjab, Pakistan. *PLOS Global Public Health*, 2(9).

Ali, S.H., Foster, T. and Hall, N.L. 2018. The relationship between infectious diseases and housing maintenance in Indigenous Australian households. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(12), p.2827.

Andualem, Z., Taddese, A.A., Azene, Z.N., Azanaw, J. and Dagne, H. 2020. Respiratory symptoms and associated risk factors among under-five children in Northwest, Ethiopia: community based cross-sectional study. *Multidisciplinary Respiratory Medicine*, 15(1), p.685.

Anwar, N., Kirychuk, S., Karunanayake, C.P., Ramsden, V., Thompson, B., Russell, E., McMullin, K., Rennie, D., Seesequasis, J., Fenton, M. and Abonyi, S. 2021. Associations between housing factors and respiratory symptoms in two Saskatchewan First Nations communities. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(7), p.3744.

Avčin, B.A., Kučina, A.U., Šarotar, B.N., Radovanović, M. and Plesničar, B.K. 2011. The present global financial and economic crisis poses an additional risk factor for mental health problems on the employees. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 23(SUPPL. 1), pp. S142–S148.

Azanaw, J., Weldegebriel, F. and Malede, A. 2024. Investigating neighborhood environmental risk factors associated with childhood acute respiratory infection symptoms in Ethiopia: mixed effect and multilevel logistic regression analysis based on EDHS 2016. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, p.1391682.

Balashova, S.A., Reshetnikova, M.S., Kadrov, V.M., Vasilieva, G.A. and Rogozhina, N.A. 2025. A sustainable path to modernization: Transforming African cities. *Unconventional Resources*, p.100194.

Bronfenbrenner, U. 1979. *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Harvard University Press.

Broto, V.C., Kirshner, J., Hiteva, R. and McGregor, A. 2018. Energy poverty and health: A systematic review of the evidence. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 45, pp.88–99.

Brugge, D., Rice, P.W., Terry, P., Howard, L. and Best, J. 2001. Housing conditions and respiratory health in a Boston public housing community. *New Solutions: A Journal of Environmental and Occupational Health Policy*, 11(2), pp.149–164.

Buthelezi, N., Leboto-Khetsi, L. and Nel, V., 2024. Ending Extreme Poverty and Enhancing Urban Health. In *Sustainable Development Goals and Urban Health: Strides, Challenges and Way Forward for Poor Neighborhoods* (pp. 13-31). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

Carbone, M., Yang, H. and Pass, H.I. 2022. Mesothelioma: Current understanding and future directions. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, 19(5), pp.300–315. doi:10.1038/s41571-021-00558-3.

Centre for Affordable Housing Finance. 2024. *Housing finance in Africa yearbook: 15th edition*.

Chatindiara, K., Marais, L. and Cloete, J., 2022. Housing and child health in South Africa: the value of longitudinal research. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(5), p.2497.

Chastonay, A.H. and Chastonay, O.J. 2022. Housing risk factors of four tropical neglected diseases: A brief review of the recent literature. *Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease*, 7(7), p.143.

Cohen, H.W., Moller, H. and Lowry, R. 2023. Asbestos exposure and lung cancer: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 65(1), pp.12–20. doi:10.1097/JOM.0000000000002217.

Connolly, M.A., Gayer, M., Ryan, M.J., Salama, P., Spiegel, P. and Heymann, D.L. 2004. Communicable diseases in complex emergencies: Impact and challenges. *The Lancet*, 364(9449), pp.1974–1983.

Corburn, J., Vlahov, D., Mberu, B., Riley, L., Caiaffa, W.T., Rashid, S.F., Ko, A., Patel, S., Jukur, S., Martínez-Herrera, E., Jayasinghe, S., Agarwal, S., Nguendo-Yongsi, B., Weru, J., Ouma, S., Edmundo, K., Oni, T. and Ayad, H. 2020. Slum health: Arresting COVID-19 and improving well-being in urban informal settlements. *Journal of Urban Health*, 97(3), pp.348–357. doi:10.1007/s11524-020-00438-6.

Culwick Fatti, J. and Khanyile, N. 2023. The impact of energy poverty on food security in South Africa. *Journal of Energy in Southern Africa*, 34(1), pp.2–11.

Culwick, C. and Patel, Z., 2020. Building just and sustainable cities through government housing developments. *Environment and Urbanization*, 32(1), pp.133-154.

Echazú, A., Bonanno, D., Juarez, M., Cajal, S.P., Heredia, V., Caropresi, S., Cimino, R.O., Caro, N., Vargas, P.A., Paredes, G. and Krolewiecki, A.J. 2015. Effect of poor access to water and sanitation as risk factors for soil-transmitted helminth infection: Selectiveness by the infective route. *PLOS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 9(9), art. no. e0004111. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004111.

Economou, M., Charitsi, M., Peppou, L.E., Dieti, E. and Souliotis, K. 2018. Mental health in Greece during the economic crisis: Socioeconomic determinants of depression. *Archives of Hellenic Medicine*, 35, pp.17-26.

Ergönül, Ö., Keske, Ş., Ksinzik, A., Güldan, M., Özbek, L., Azap, A., Şimşek-Yavuz, S., Can, F. and Sakarya, S., 2023. The challenges in the monitoring of infectious diseases after the earthquake in Türkiye in 2023. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases*, 23(11), pp.e482-e488.

Evans, G.W., Wells, N.M. and Moch, A., 2003. Housing and mental health: a review of the evidence and a methodological and conceptual critique. *Journal of social issues*, 59(3), pp.475-500.

García-Searcy, V., Villada-Canela, M., Arredondo-García, M.C., Anglés-Hernández, M., Pelayo-Torres, M.C. and Daesslé, L.W., 2022. Sanitation in Mexico: an overview of its realization as a human right. *Sustainability*, 14(5), p.2707.

Gazin, P. and Brouqui, P., 2004. Infectious diseases in homeless persons. *Antibiotiques*, 6(3), pp.175-179.

Gbadegesin, J., Pienaar, M., Marais, L 2020. Housing, planning and urban health: historical and current perspectives from South Africa. *Bulletin of Geography. Socio-economic Series*, No. 48 (2020): 23–34.

Ghinai, I., Davis, E.S., Mayer, S., Toews, K.A., Huggett, T.D., Snow-Hill, N., Perez, O., Hayden, M.K., Tehrani, S., Landi, A.J. and Crane, S., 2020, November. Risk factors for severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 infection in homeless shelters in Chicago, Illinois—March–May 2020. *In Open forum infectious diseases* (Vol. 7, No. 11, p. ofaa477). US: Oxford University Press.

Guerra, O. and Eboeime, E., 2021. The impact of economic recessions on depression, anxiety, and trauma-related disorders and illness outcomes scoping review. *Behavioral sciences*, 11(9), p.119.

Habib, A.R., Stella, S.A., Farkouh, E.K., Grenko, C.M., Hart, D. and Pasha, A.S., 2025. Recommitting Housing and Health Care Justice After City of Grants Pass v Johnson. *American Journal of Public Health*, 115(1), pp.18-22.

Haselbach, L., Hussey, J., Feigley, C.E., Hebert, J.R., White, D.W. & Lawson, A., 2009. Airborne transmission via HVAC of acute respiratory infections in military facilities? *Journal of Green Building*, 4(1), pp.114-120.

Herath, S., Mansour, A. & Bentley, R., 2024. Urban density, household overcrowding and the spread of COVID-19 in Australian cities. *Health & Place*, 89, art. no. 103298.

Hodgson, J.T., 2020. The link between asbestos and cancer: An overview. *Occupational Medicine*, 70(8), pp.550-558. doi:10.1093/occmed/kqaa099.

Holden, K.A., Lee, A.R., Hawcutt, D.B. & Sinha, I.P., 2023. The impact of poor housing and indoor air quality on respiratory health in children. *Breathe*, 19(2).

Ismail, Z. & Khembo, A., 2015. The impact of energy poverty on health outcomes in South Africa. *Energy Policy*, 87, pp. 30-39.

Jabali, O., Ayyoub, A.A., Jabali, S. and Saeedi, M., 2025. Examining the nexus between housing conditions and health outcomes in Palestinian society: a mixed-method investigation. *BMC Public Health*, 25, p.560.

Kann, R.S., Snyder, J. S., Victor, C., Cumbe, Z.A., Garn, J.V., McGunegill, S., Nalá, R., Matthew C., Levy, K (2024). Water, sanitation, and hygiene insecurity and disease prevention behaviors during the COVID-19 pandemic in low-income neighborhoods of Beira, Mozambique. *PLoS ONE*, 19. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0310490

Kararach, G., 2024. South Africa: Economic Policies to Promote Equality and Achieve High-Income Status. In *Avoiding the Middle-Income Trap in Africa: Economic Challenges and Policy Responses* (pp. 123-168). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

Karb, R., Samuels, E., Vanjani, R., Trimbur, C. and Napoli, A., 2020. Homeless shelter characteristics and prevalence of SARS-CoV-2. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 21(5), p.1048.

Katukiza, A.Y., Ronteltap, M., Niwagaba, C.B., Foppen, J.W.A., Kansiime, F.P.N.L. and Lens, P.N.L., 2012. Sustainable sanitation technology options for urban slums. *Biotechnology advances*, 30(5), pp.964-978. DOI: 10.1016/j.biotechadv.2012.02.007

Kawachi, I. & Berkman, L.F., 2001. Social ties and health: A review of literature. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 5(1), pp.1-14.

Kelly, J.D., Barrie, M.B., Ross, R.A., Temple, B.A., Moses, L.M. and Bausch, D.G., 2013. Housing equity for health equity: a rights-based approach to the control of Lassa fever in post-war Sierra Leone. *BMC international health and human rights*, 13, pp.1-6.

Kishore, Surekha; Venkatesh, U; Verma, Shikhar Kishore; Verma, Shival Kishore; Walia, Parateek (2023). Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene: *A Global Imperative for Health*, *Indian Journal of Community Health*, 35 (3), pp. 367 – 371. doi: 10.47203/IJCH.2023.v35i03.022

Kua, K.P. & Lee, D.S.W.H., 2021. Home environmental interventions for prevention of respiratory tract infections: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Reviews on Environmental Health*, 36(3), pp.297-307.

Kyne, Dean 2023. A Bird's-Eye View of Colonias Hosting Forgotten Americans and Their Community Resilience in the Rio Grande Valley. *Geographies*, 3 (3), pp. 459 - 476, DOI: 10.3390/geographies3030024.

Leboto-Khetsi, L., Kohima, J., Gambe, T.R., Mphambukeli, T.N. and Rammile, S., 2024. Liveability Assessment in South Africa's Hostel Accommodation: Implications for Urban Health and Sustainable Development Goal 11. In *Sustainable Development Goals and Urban Health: Strides, Challenges and Way Forward for Poor Neighborhoods* (pp. 97-115). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.

Leta, L.T., 2021. 'It was no different to a prison camp': Oral accounts of adaptations, transitions and surviving an 'emergency camp'; from Sophiatown to Ammunition Depot 91, 1955–1960s. *HTS Theologiese Studies/Theological Studies*, 77(2).

Liu, Q., Deng, J., Yan, W., Qin, C., Du, M., Wang, Y., Zhang, S., Liu, M. and Liu, J., 2024. Burden and trends of infectious disease mortality are attributed to air pollution, unsafe water, sanitation, and hygiene, and non-optimal temperature globally and in different socio-demographic index regions. *Global Health Research and Policy*, 9(1), p.23.

Marais, L. (2013). Housing and health in South Africa: A review of the literature. *Journal of Housing Studies*, 28(1), 1-12.

Marais, L., Hoekstra, J., Napier, M., Cloete, J. and Lenka, M., 2018. The housing careers of black middle-class residents in a South African metropolitan area. *Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*, 33, pp.843-860.

Marmot, M. G., (2010). The Marmot Review: Strategic Review of Health Inequalities in England post-2010. *Lancet*, 376(9753), 215-235.

Masuku, M., 2024. The state of energy poverty in South Africa: A focus on Gauteng. *Energy Policy*, 172, p.112823.

Masuku, B. and Nzewi, O., 2021. The South African informal sector's socio-economic exclusion from basic service provisions: A critique of Buffalo City Metropolitan Municipality's approach to the informal sector. *Journal of Energy in Southern Africa*, 32(2), pp.59-71.

Moffa, M., Cronk, R., Fejfar, D., Dancausse, S., Padilla, L.A. & Bartram, J., 2019. A systematic scoping review of environmental health conditions and hygiene behaviors in homeless shelters. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, 222(3), pp. 335-346.

Moyo, H.T., Zuidgeest, M. and van Delden, H., 2021. Lessons learned from applying an integrated land use transport planning model to address issues of social and economic exclusion of marginalized groups: The case of Cape Town, South Africa. *Urban Science*, 5(1), p.10.

Musango, J.K., 2014. The health impacts of energy poverty in South Africa. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 38, pp. 1-8.

Narayan, A.S., Marks, S.J., Meierhofer, R., Strande, L., Tilley, E., Zurbrügg, C. & Lüthi, C., 2021. Advancements in Integration of Water, Sanitation, and Solid Waste for Low- and Middle-Income Countries. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 46, pp.193-219.

Ntema, J., Anderson, I. and Marais, L., 2021. Housing and possible health implications in upgraded informal settlements: evidence from Mangaung township, South Africa. In *Housing and SDGs in Urban Africa* (pp. 71-85). Singapore: Springer Singapore.

Nvo-Fernandez, M., Miño-Reyes, V., Serrano, C., Acosta-Antognoni, H., Salas, F., Wiedeman, C.V., Ahumada-Méndez, F. and Leiva-Bianchi, M., 2025. What Is the Impact of Unemployment as an Adverse Experience? Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder and Complex Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder: A Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 22(5), p.696.

Nuwagaba, A. (2018). Urban poverty and environmental health: The case of Kampala city, Uganda, *Human Impact on Environment and Sustainable Development in Africa*, pp. 403 – 428. DOI: 10.4324/9781315192963-17

Nyashanu, M., Simbanegavi, P. and Gibson, L., 2020. Exploring the impact of COVID-19 pandemic lockdown on informal settlements in Tshwane Gauteng Province, South Africa. *Global Public Health*, 15(10), pp.1443-1453.

Ortega, D.R., Esquivel, D.F.G., Ayala, T.B., Pineda, B., Manzo, S.G., Quino, J.M., Mora, P.C. and de la Cruz, V.P., 2021. Cognitive impairment induced by lead exposure during lifespan: Mechanisms of lead neurotoxicity. *Toxics*, 9(2), p.23.

Parikh, S., Henderson, K., Gondalia, R., Kaye, L., Remmelink, E., Thompson, A., & Barrett, M. 2022. Perceptions of Environmental Influence and Environmental Information-Seeking Behavior Among People with Asthma and COPD, *Frontiers in Digital Health*, 4, art. no. 748400. DOI: 10.3389/fdgth.2022.748400

Penrose, K., De Castro, M. C., Werema, J., Ryan, E.T. 2010. Informal urban settlements and cholera risk in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 4 (3). DOI: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0000631

Ralli, M., Arcangeli, A., Morrone, A. and Ercoli, L., 2021. Homeless shelter characteristics and prevalence of SARS-CoV-2. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 22(2), p.232.

Reid, A., de Klerk, N.H. and Musk, A.W., 2021. The role of asbestos in the development of lung cancer and mesothelioma: A review. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), p.1123. doi:10.1186/s12889-021-11123-4.

Rennie, D.C.; Lawson, J.A. (2011). Respiratory protection: Domestic air quality and lung health, *Minerva Pneumologica*, 50 (1), pp. 31 – 4.

Rogers, J.H., Hawes, S.E., Wolf, C.R., Hughes, J.P., Englund, J.A., Starita, L.M. and Chu, H.Y., 2023. Care-seeking correlates of acute respiratory illness among sheltered adults experiencing

homelessness in Seattle, WA, 2019: a community-based cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 11, p.1090148.

Samarakoon, S., 2019. A justice and well-centered framework for analyzing energy poverty in the Global South. *Ecological Economics*, 165, p.106385.

Seekings, J., 2011. Race, class, and inequality in the South African city. *The new Blackwell companion to the city*, pp.532-546.

Swope, C.B. and Hernández, D., 2019. Housing as a determinant of health equity: A conceptual model. *Social science & medicine*, 243, p.112571.

Shahzad, L. 2025. Outbreak of epidemics during disaster response. *The Routledge Handbook of Disaster Response and Recovery*, pp. 202 – 216. DOI: 10.4324/9781003414834-22

Sharif, N., Dey, S. K 2024. Infectious Diseases and Global Health Inequity, *Integrated Science*, 22, pp. 11 – 22. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-60502-4_2

Sharma, D., Kuppusamy, K. and Bhoorasamy, A., 2013. Prevalence of acute respiratory infections (ARI) and their determinants in under five children in urban and rural areas of Kancheepuram district, South India. *Annals of Tropical Medicine & Public Health*, 6(5).

Shortt, N.K. and Hammett, D., 2013. Housing and health in an informal settlement upgrade in Cape Town, South Africa. *Journal of housing and the built environment*, 28(4), pp.615-627.

Shukla, J.B., Naresh, R., Verma, S.R., Agarwal. 2020. Modeling the effect of sanitation in a human habitat to control the spread of bacterial diseases. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 6 (1), pp. 39 - 49, DOI: 10.1007/s40808-019-00653-4

Sinha, Braj Raj Kumar(2021). Upgrading Slums in India, *Advances in 21st Century Human Settlements*, pp. 431 - 443, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-15-5608-1_33

Smith, R., 2023. Understanding the policy landscape of energy poverty in South Africa. *African Journal of Public Affairs*, 15(1), pp.24-35.

Sovacool, B.K., et al., 2022. Energy poverty and the role of renewable energy in South Africa. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 141, p.110788.

Stull, V., Bell, M.M. and Ncwadi, M., 2016. Environmental apartheid: Eco-health and rural marginalization in South Africa. *Journal of rural studies*, 47, pp.369-380.

Turley R; Saith, R; Bhan, N; Rehfuess, E; Carter. 2013. Slum upgrading strategies involving physical environment and infrastructure interventions and their effects on health and socio-economic outcomes, *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 2013 (1), DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD010067.pub2

Turok, I., Todes, A., & Smit, W., 2022. Urbanization and housing in South Africa: Trends, challenges, and opportunities. *Urban Forum*, 33(2), pp. 249-267.

Tusting, L.S., Bisanzio, D., Alabaster, G., Cameron, E., Cibulskis, R., Davies, M., Flaxman, S., Gibson, H.S., Knudsen, J., Mbogo, C. and Okumu, F.O., 2019. Mapping changes in housing in sub-Saharan Africa from 2000 to 2015. *Nature*, 568(7752), pp.391-394.

Usha, J.; Nithiya, S. 2024. Water and Sanitation: A Global Priority. *Water Resources Development and Management*, Part F2884, pp. 369 - 380, DOI: 10.1007/978-981-99-8639-2_18

Van Mark, A. Kessel, R., Pleimes, D., Welte, T., Groneberg, D. A. 2007. Environment and lung diseases - Current aspects. *Arbeitsmedizin Sozialmedizin Umweltmedizin*, 42 (1), pp. 16 – 21.

Waddell, C.J., Saldana, C.S., Schoonveld, M.M., Meehan, A.A., Lin, C.K., Butler, J.C. and Mosites, E., 2024. Infectious diseases among people experiencing homelessness: a systematic review of the literature in the United States and Canada, 2003-2022. *Public Health Reports*, 139(5), pp.532-548.

Whitehead, J., Pearson, A.L., Lawrenson, R. and Atatoa-Carr, P., 2019. Spatial equity and realized access to healthcare—a geospatial analysis of general practitioner enrolments in Waikato, New Zealand. *Rural and remote health*, 19(4), pp.1-13.

Wimalasena, N.N., Chang-Richards, A., Wang, K.I.K. and Dirks, K.N., 2021. Housing risk factors associated with respiratory disease: a systematic review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(6), p.2815.

World Health Organisation (WHO), 2022. Asbestos: Elimination of asbestos-related diseases. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/asbestos>.

World Health Organization, 2018. Housing and health guidelines. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241550395>.

Wyman, K.M. and Spiegel-Feld, D., 2020. The urban environmental renaissance. *California Law Review*, 108(2), pp.305-377.

Wu, K., Strane, D., Kellom, K., Stokes, S., Brunisholz, K., Rubin, D., Klusaritz, H. and Cronholm, P.F., 2024. Implementing the Population-Based Social Determinants of Health Intervention: Early Lessons Learned from Collaboration between Clinical and Community Organizations. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved*, 35(3), pp.933-950.

Yasui, A. and Numada, M. 2021. A report on the questionnaire survey on awareness of covid-19 and shelters. *Journal of Disaster Research*, 16(4), pp.747-764.

Zuber, M., Khosla, C. and Javed, N.B., 2023. Housing Conditions and Their Impact on Health of Residents. *Engineering Proceedings*, 56(1), p.46.